

SZ-A-01 Registration at BIRD via BUND-ID (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090359
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Title	Registration at BIRD via BUND-ID
Educational area	#general
Persona	P: Alvin - Legal guardian https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091406
Short description	Alvin wants to use BIRD and the wallet with the highest level of trust, to transfer sensitive documents and data, and logs in with the BUND user account.
Result	Alvin has linked his BIRD account to the BUND user account and has uploaded additional documents and attributes to the Data-Wallet.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Registration at BUND.ID"• Part 2: "Registration at BIRD via BUND.ID and linking the wallet"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Alvin has an identity card with an activated online ID function• Alvin has the AusweisApp2 on his smartphone
Components	#data-wallet #dataeditor
Services / tools	#bundid #ausweisapp2

Problem scenario

Introduction

Alvin and his family are about to move to a new state and thus entering a new phase of life. This transition involves various bureaucratic processes, which place an additional burden for Alvin and his wife. Alvin wants to simplify these processes as much as possible and is open to trying new digital services. For example, he needs an up-to-date certificate of good conduct for work, a new registration certificate, and various documents for his daughters' school transfer. In addition, he still has to apply for financial support for his daughter.

Problem definition

Alvin needs to gather several documents and submit them to his daughters' new school. Obtaining certified copies would require a visit to the notary which would result in additional costs. He would also have to go to a copy shop for the uncertified copies, since he no longer has a printer at home. Due to infrequent use and the high cost of printer cartridges, he decided to sell his printer and is now looking for a way to provide the document to the school digitally. However, the school still needs to ensure the authenticity of the documents.

Background and context

Last year, Alvin replaced his old ID card with a new one with an online identification (ID) function. He has already applied for a certificate of good conduct for his new job and likes the availability of digital citizen services. He is now also considering registering with the Federal Employment Agency via the [BundID](#) user account.

Alvin already uses a Data-Wallet, which stores not only his own documents and data but also those of his daughter. Since he needs these documents for the school transfer, the easiest solution would be to share them directly with the new school without major detours.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Alvin is already very stressed by the move. He would prefer to complete all the bureaucratic processes in one session on the computer rather than having to visit multiple authorities. Since he no longer has a printer at Home, sending applications by post would require a trip to the copy shop and the purchase of stamps. Between work and moving preparations, he has little time left and is usually exhausted in the evenings. He worries about overlooking something and having to repeat tasks.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Alvin has already contacted the children's new school by phone. He was offered the option of sending the necessary documents by mail. Alternatively, he could use BIRD if, provided he has a high level of trust and the documents in his wallet are verified. This seems to be the better option for Alvin.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Registration at ([BundID](#))"

Step 1: Alvin wants to use all of BIRD's features without restriction and link his EUDI-wallet to BIRD, so he decides to register with the highest level of trust.

Step 2: Alvin opens the page [BundID](#) and selects "create account".

Step 3: On the BundID website, Alvin sees several options for creating an account. He chooses the "Online ID" option.

Step 4: Alvin selects his identity card with online functionality and accepts the privacy policy consent form.

Step 5: Alvin follows the instructions on the website. For this, he needs the AusweisApp2 on his smartphone, his ID card with online functionality, and his 6-digit PIN. Once he has created his account, Alvin has a BUND user account, which he can use to register on BIRD.

Part 2: "Registration at BIRD via BUND.ID and linking the wallet"

Step 1: Alvin opens BIRD and selects "Login" on the home page.

Step 2: Alvin selects "log in with my Bund.ID" and enters his Bund.ID login details.

Step 3: Through the login process, a verified user account is created. Alvin can now connect his Data-Wallet to his BIRD account on the home page.

Step 4: By logging in with his BundID user account, Alvin gains access to new verified attributes in the data editor, which he can transfer to his Data-Wallet. These attributes are retrieved from his online ID card.

Step 5: Alvin can now share documents and files for the children's new school via BIRD and the data editor.

Step 6: He notices that some documents are still missing from the wallet, but he has them in print. Using the wallet's OCR function, he can scan the documents and have them verified.